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Research Article

Brand Positioning by Chinese Mobile phones Brands in Uganda

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Abstract: *It's no coincidence that a growing number of Africa's most popular phones are manufactured in China. For years, Chinese mobile manufacturers have had practice in developing affordable smartphones for a growing market. Tecno, Infinix, Itel, Huawei, Oppo, Vivo are major Chinese mobile brands in Uganda. Brand positioning is built on a foundation of great strategies. It plays a crucial role while deciding the strategy of an organization. Chinese companies took initiatives to understand what consumers want, understand what their brand capabilities are and finally understood how each competitor is positioning their brand then they reflect this brand positioning in everything that they did. As a result, Chinese mobile brands have become leading, convenient and affordable mobile phones brand.*

Keywords: *Brand Management, Brand Positioning, Mobile phones brands, Transsion, China in Africa, Uganda.*

Introduction

Brands are the essence of firms. They create market share, increase customer loyalty, strengthen network power, offer the impending for higher profit margins, and guard against competitive doses” [1]. It can be defined as "a name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or combination of them which is intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competitors [2]. Crafting strong organizational brands has become a central theme in marketing and organizational of business entities. An organization's brand is the rational image that a consumer has when he or she hears the name. On the most essential level, the brand may incorporate the association's logo, shading mix, or motto. In any case, examine demonstrates that an association's image is considerably more than a visual or sound-related message; it speaks to the whole personality dependent on a person's encounters with the association, the strategic

exercises of the association, and its examples of overcoming adversity [3]. Marking is a fundamental part of an organization's promoting endeavours and results in both natural and extraneous incentive to organizations; consequently, for a fruitful business it is critical to situate a brand in a compelling way.

Brand Positioning

Brand positioning can essentially be characterized as the demonstration of structuring the organization's contribution and picture to possess a particular spot in the psyche of the objective market. As such, brand situating depicts how a brand is unique in relation to its rivals and where, or how, it sits in clients' brains [4] which includes creating brand relationship in clients' psyches to cause them to see the brand with a particular goal in mind [5].

Brands encourage direction among and decision between specific items or administrations, and in this way unburden the purchaser. Brands exert three major purposes: an information purpose, a risk-reduction purpose, and an image purpose. In their hazard decrease work, brands fill in as a sign and verification of value. They fill in as a wellbeing measure, which inspires trust in the eye of the client. Finally, it is becoming increasingly important for organisations to acknowledge the identity-creating effect of a brand. The identity-creating effect is the result of the projection of a brand's character onto the personality of the consumer, which then contributes to the creation of social prestige [6].

Uganda Mobile phones Industry

More Africans and particularly Ugandans are buying Tecno Brand phones from Transsion as compared to the traditional Samsung and I phone as more people are embracing the smart phone. It's no coincidence that a growing number of Africa's most popular phones Ugandan Cellphone market in particular are manufactured in China. East Africa's smartphone market is growing due to the large population of young people and the increasing adoption of technology in this developing region, while the relatively calmer economic climate also helped spur the growth throughout 2019. Demand for smartphones remains very high in East Africa. According to the market intelligence reports, TECNO models top the chat of bestselling models in Uganda. Samsung models have been relegated. Reports of the third quarter of 2017, indicate out of ten selling models, Tecno had six .One of China's biggest smartphone makers has never sold a handset in the country. Yet thousands of miles away, it dominates markets across Africa. The Chinese brands Tecno, Huawei , ITEL, Infinix , Oppo and Xiaomi account for more than 85% of total

smartphone shipments in East Africa. Thee Unknown in the West, Transsion has left global players like Samsung and Apple trailing in its wake in a continent that's home to more than a billion people. For years, Chinese mobile manufacturers have had practice in developing affordable smartphones for a growing market. When Transsion (TECNO) went public on Shanghai's NASDAQ-style stock exchange Sept. 30 topping a \$6.5 billion market cap, the industry was a-buzz around the little-known manufacturer from Shenzhen, China whose brands, Tecno and Infinix have grown rapidly to make it Africa's No.1 maker of cell phones in just a few short years. But what has received much less notice is the host of other Chinese-owned cell phone makers gaining traction in the African mobile phone market especially in Uganda. In coming years, we can expect to see more of these firms make major moves in the African mobile phone market [7]. Transsion's listing prospectus listed nine other phone brands gaining traction in the African mobile phone market, five of those, with a combined 18.7% market share, also had Chinese roots and were not just OEM partners but brand owners and licensees

Brand awareness

Over the past year, Oppo and Vivo phones have made aggressive inroads into the African market. Walk through Kampala's central business district on any given day and both companies' green and blue signs can be seen from down the block, balloon towers raised and music blasting from each stand. Oppo gadgets are marketed heavily with one vendor claiming, "Oppo is currently selling better than any other brands". If a customer isn't keen on Oppo, they are quickly directed to the new Vivo 17. But, when asked for the distinguishing features between the two brands there was little to be said. The phones tote different names, but they essentially come from the same place and DNA. Vivo and Oppo are sub-brands of BKK Electronics Company, a private, multinational tech hardware company based in Shenzhen, China.

Samsung, which has had a strong presence in most African markets with its feature phones, has lost market share overall rather than gain as more users upgrade to Chinese-made smartphones [8]. Tecno and Itel's parents company, Transsion Holdings, is the dark horse of china's tech sector. Though the company has a low profile in its home city in Shenzhen, the southern startup hub is also home to Huawei and nearly 40million more than Xiaomi.

Transsion enjoys a market share of over 50% in Africa and is the top vendor for both feature phones -cheaper handsets with basic functions and smartphones. The company's success has been built on

a decision made two years after it developed its first feature phone, the Tecno T201 in 2006, to focus exclusively on Africa. Transsion believed there was a unique growth opportunity there.

Positioning

Positioning of a product refers to creating a good image of the product in the minds of the customer by bringing out a logo which is easily recognized by the customer, also a standard ringtone & message tone and try to highlight the advantages of the product. This specific aspect must be embedded into the mindset of the customer so that whenever they hear the ringtone or see the logo, they can associate it with our product. It can also be termed as how a brand is different from its competitors and where, or how, it sits in customers' minds. A brand positioning strategy therefore involves creating brand associations in customers' minds to make them perceive the brand in a specific way . Back in 2011, when cell phones were increasingly popular in China, but out of reach for those outside of China's metropolises like Beijing and Shanghai, "shanzhai" mobile phone makers filled a void where popular phones could not. What they developed were simple and affordable imitations of the hottest products on the market. As they gained loyal customers in less traditional markets, they began to branch out and create products with distinct features that rivalled the very best. But, as more "shanzhai" mobile phone makers grew in business, they hit walls at home. Research indicates that an organization's brand is much more than a visual or auditory message; it represents the entire identity based on an individual's experiences with the organization, the mission and activities of the organization, and its success stories. In East Africa , Uganda in particular ,the market was saturated, incomes were rising, and consumer tastes began to shift toward phones with better brand recognition. Realizing decreasing profits at home, these firms saw new promise in the African mobile phone market. It was through massive rebranding and sub-branding campaigns that the "shanzhai" mobile phones became the standard for the African mobile phone market. Branding is an integral component of a company's marketing efforts and results in both intrinsic and extrinsic value to companies; hence for a successful business it is important to position a brand in an effective manner

In order to create a unique and successful positioning for their brand in Ugandan mobile phone market, Chinese companies took initiatives to understand what consumers want, understand what are their brand capabilities and finally understood how each competitor is positioning their brand

then they reflect this brand positioning in everything that they did. As a result Chinese mobile brands has become leading, convenient and affordable mobile phones brand.

Chinese mobile brand Manufactures segmented the market by gender, Income and Age. Gender by bringing out cell phones of different colour as female are generally attracted towards bright colour such as pink, red, white etc. Female generally go for mini, slim, light weight phones. Income by segmenting the market according to income through bringing out cell phones of different price range as there are different people in our country with different income level. Age- A person's taste varies with his age, like an old person would want a simple phone which would only serve his purpose of calling where as a middle age person would look for a business or smart phone which would keep him up-to-date with his mail and business. Whereas a teenage would be looking for a hi-tech multimedia set with all facilities for entertainment like camera, music player, internet facilities, games etc.

Marketing Mix

It is about putting the right product or a combination thereof in the place, at the right time, and at the right price with the right promotion strategy The success of its leading phone brands Tecno, ITEL and Infinix has especially shown how a company with strong regional focus , the right product mix and strategic pricing can outperform bigger more dominant firms. The Shenzhen based company's rise has also coincided with a rising appetite for smartphones in Africa, encouraged by cheaper internet costs and increasing mobile based innovation. By betting on local consumers long undeserved by tech giants. The Chinese brand has shown that you ignore emerging markets at your own risk.

Product: The product is the centre of the marketing mix and the other three P's are based around it. Consumers purchase goods and services for a variety of individual reasons and a company must be aware of all of these when selling a product. Transsion's brands (Tecno, Infinix ,ITEL) dominated the East African smartphone market accounting for 70.8% of total shipments in 2019. Chinese mobile phones manufacturers do exactly the same and comes up with innovative phones almost every six months. Tecno, Infinix, ITEL, Huawei, Oppo, Vivo are major Chinese mobile brands in Uganda. They have successfully achieved "giving consumers what they want" reflected for example in Tecno's motto "think global, act local," which meant making phones that met Africans' specific needs. With more innovations followed, Transsion opened research and development centers in China, Nigeria and Kenya to work out how to better appeal to African users. Local

languages such as Amharic, Hausa and Swahili were added to keyboards and phones were given a longer battery life.

Price: Price is a key factor in the selling of a product, and is usually the one that is open to most change based on different pricing strategies, for example, competitor based, penetration or skimming. The three main factors affecting the amount charged for a product or service are cost of production, customer demand and competition. Chinese Mobile phones brands are offered at different pricing strategies based on each type. Chinese mobile manufacturers have had practice in developing affordable smartphones for African growing market. But perhaps Transsion's smartest move was its pricing. It has three main brands: Tecno mobile, Infinix and Itel. Most of their feature and smartphones sell for between fifteen dollars and two hundred dollars. As some of the Chinese brand smartphones are priced from as low as the equivalent of fifty dollars, this is why more expensive global leaders like Apple's iPhone and upmarket Samsung models do not feature strongly in most African markets. This price sensitivity is especially relevant as more people upgrade from feature phones to smartphones to use popular services like WhatsApp and Instagram. Africa continues to be price sensitive market with almost three fifth of total handsets sales being sold approximately below one hundred dollars. There are still users who are now experiencing their first ever smart phone and Transsion is wooing these customers by providing them with aggressive specs at an affordable price. Transsion's cheap phones were once perceived as unfashionable by the African consumers on the market. However, the company has moved up the value chain and is increasingly competing directly against other global brands launching a higher end smartphone only brand named Infinix in 2013. These low prices and high brand reputation will help Transsion remain popular among first time smartphone buyers. Other brands are likely to target users buying second or third handsets according to counterpoint Research.

Place: It refers to chosen outlets for a product or service, for a product to be successful it must be easy to access. Now a day's mobile phones are easy to access as they are available in supermarkets, company and specialized outlets (Mobile Store).

Promotions: This involves providing information regarding the product to the customers through various media platforms. Chinese mobile phones brands mainly promotes its business through Print Advertising, Outdoor Advertising, Covert Advertising, Surrogate Advertising, Celebrity Advertising and Broadcasting Advertising. In the streets of Kampala Uganda ,shoppers are ambushed by vast stretched banners in blue and red advertising Tecno brand mobile the biggest

selling mobile phones in the town. The Promotion also informs the customer about various offers and discount which is offered. Transsion plays down its Chinese roots. "In Africa, we say that we are African," which explains why Tecno's stores carry no Chinese characters or signs of being a Chinese brand. This assimilates them with local market. Transsion has higher brand recognition and is better attuned to the needs of its users. Tecno rose to seventh on Brand Africa's list of the top most one hundred admired brands in Africa. ITEL and Infinix mobiles also made it on the list respectively. Transsion's long-term investment in relationship building and training local staff have helped promote brand loyalty.

SWOT Analysis

Strength

Provides many functions at much lower costs, e.g. Android OS, 8MP camera, AMOLED screen, Dual sim etc. Regional languages support, Easy to operate and phones cabinets are made with fibre as it can easily be replaced at low-cost if damaged. Most phones are dual SIM/Triple SIM phone. Due to Android OS we can get a huge number of applications from the android market. High durability, hard and efficient screens and in case of screen replacement, it's not costly compared to other brands. Manufacturing efficiency as the battery system is very efficient and they also have a user-friendly interface. These phones also have a superior reputation in the country. They are cheap and readily available to everyone.

Weakness

After-sales customer service not present as the luxurious brands like Apple and Samsung due to the fact that most of these brands are sold in retail outlets that can open and close at any given time. Many consumers in this group still trust Apple, Samsung as they have a good brand name and goodwill in this section of market. Lack of competitive comprehensive platform for hardware, software and services. Poor quality is inferior, high radiation levels and small screens.

Opportunities

Low-end phones market has become very competitive, Cut-throat competition has made Dual-SIM phones being available.

Fast growing smartphone market. Low price phones are high in demand. High growth in other developing regions.

Threats

The same industry competitive. Threat from well-known brands like Apple, Nokia, Samsung, HTC and Other lower end phones brands like Karbonn Mobiles, Micromax Mobiles, Lava Mobiles, Lemon Mobiles. Incapable to continuously adapt to the sudden change in technological advancements.

Brand competitive analysis

Value proposition for the mobile phones. The companies are innovative as these phones come in various colours with many attractive features and functions hence making it easy for them to reach their target market. The phones help the customers to express themselves, have a superior taste and also a high durability.

The winning Strategy

Transsion has been on a sustained toll pushing out devices that walk and talk like Samsung. But most importantly, these phones cost a price of Samsung models. For example, replacing damaged Samsung screen Samsung S5 costs five hundred thousand Ugandan shillings (500000), the cost of brand new Tecno C5 with similar or even better features. Numbers don't lie, Samsung SMj110FZKAAFR, for the third quarter of 2017 sold phones worth 527124000 Ugandan shillings, TECNO L8 sold phones totalling 464342005, TECNO W4 424338001, Tecno Y2408323000, Tecno C9391822000, TecnoW3 388242000. In Africa, its also diversifying its footprint. Transsion has set up a second facility in Ethiopia where workers assemble both phones and LED televisions under its household appliance brand Syinix. With over 1900 employees in Ethiopia alone now, working in warehouses . Transsion says its keen on exploring and setting up in more African markets.

Expansion Strategy analysis

To support its African sales network Transcom maintains a manufacturing facility in Ethiopia. The company even announced plans to build an industrial park and an R&D facility in India to manufacture phones for African countries thus boasting its control in the East African market. Along Kampala Road, there are more than 30 branded Tecno shops. Even the prominent telecom shops, like Simba Telecom are now full of Tecno models as opposed to Samsung models.

Infact any business that fails along Kampala road is taken over by Tecno mobile phones business the next day.

As a strategy, Tecno started by doing basic business in the low and end budget mobile segments from which they gained trust of customers. The telecoms in Uganda have notices the growing

giant. Today, you find Telecom giants Airtel Uganda, MTN Uganda shops, service centres selling Tecno phones and not Samsung phones. Transsion is also testing Africa as a manufacturing centre, something that could become more feasible as the African Continental free trade area comes into effect. The two manufacturing facilities in Ethiopia which is pursuing an Asia style industrial policy, in addition to factories in China, India and Bangladesh.

Together with Huawei and ZTE, Chinese equipment makers that wired up the continent virtually single handedly. Transsion has helped lead the African telecom revolution. The hardware installed; China's software developers are also coming. Alibaba has road tested its Alipay system in South Africa and WeChat has a partnership with Uganda's M-pesa mobile and mobile money offering. To be fair to western companies, some including Vodafone, Orange and Facebook , whose WhatsApp messenger service is ubiquitous, have also seen the potential of the African consumer. While most companies move into Africa as an afterthought, Transsion has done things in reverse, using Africa to innovate and to test the robustness of its offering. It is now selling phones in India and Latin America. In Africa, however the company is the king of mobile phones.

Advertising Strategy analysis

Its advertising strategy has enabled it to hold 54% of the feature phone market through its brands Tecno, Infinix, Itel. .More to this, its smartphones sales is second to Samsung and before Huawei according to International Data Corporation State. These brands have partnered with the biggest telecommunications networks like MTN (Mobile Telecommunications Network) and Airtel and this help to voice out their products, air their promotions thus creating a mass platform for these brands. The wide coverage reaches large masses all over the country. Many promotions are held and these phone brands are given out as gifts to the various winners. These brands also go forward and sponsor events that take place in the country like donating blood, screening of cervical and prostate cancer etc. This in the long run creates awareness of the brands and people ending up buying them due to the good cause of concern that they are carrying out. Their partnerships with the biggest telecommunication companies in the country helps create a large market force for them.

Brand extension Strategy

This is when a firm uses a n established brand name to introduce an established brand name to introduce a new product in the market. It comes with line extension and category extension. Transsion under it's make Tecno collaborated with MTN Uganda the biggest network in East Africa and launched the Tecno Y2 and this was launched in 2017. The Tecno Y2 was sold through

all the MTN serving centres. These phones came at a retail price making them more affordable. Six care centres offer after sales services as long as its within the warranty given.

Equity engines

This model depicts three key dimensions of brand affinity, the emotional and intangible benefits of a brand. Authority here Transsion has an outstanding reputation in the market and it has been a long-standing leader in the Ugandan phone market industry. Identification, Transsion customers using their brands like Tecno love the phones as they are very easy to navigate and the features are great thus creating a bond between the brand and the customers. Approval, the way a brand fits into the wider social matrix and the intangible status it holds for experts and friends. Transsion is seeking to build power brand that establish a broad market footprint, appealing to multiple customer segments with multiple products all underneath the brand umbrella. Despite the success of Transsion's brand (Tecno, Infinix and Itel) in both the smartphone and feature phone categories, it is also worth noting the phenomenal growth enjoyed by Huawei and its sub brand honor in Africa's smartphone space. Together these two brands saw their shipments increase by a combined 47.9% year on year in 2018, spurred by their ambitious expansion plans in emerging markets and strong focus on affordable prices.

Sales Marketing Strategy analysis

Its sales marketing strategy has also boasted its up rise in the East African Community, Uganda in particular. There are various retail outlets in all parts of the country the capital city alone has more than one hundred retail shops. These outlets are evenly spread out in all parts of the country having a maximum coverage in both rural and urban areas. Transsion brands operating in the region increased their marketing spend in Q4 2019, with an accompanying surge in sales promotions. The regions vibrant distribution network also had a positive impact on the market while online retailers were particularly successful at promoting Black Friday. To the country, this has been a very positive aspect as so many youths are interested in starting up these retail shops dealing with these phones thus creating employment opportunities for the people. The fact that these phone brands cover a wide part of the country makes it easy for people to access them. People in villages no longer have to travel to the capital city or more developed urban areas to purchase these phones.

Friendly user interface

These phones have a friendly user interface which is easy to learn and use given the fact that most people in Uganda are very illiterate when it comes to using technology. There friendly features

then make it easy for the various groups of customers to easily navigate through the phone without assistance from a third party. They have also attracted attention for being one of the first known device makers to optimise its camera phones for African complexions hence an added advantage to the brands. In Uganda, Transsion's ability to build market share and find a soft spot with consumers on price and features gives it prominence in the country's booming technology environment. These phone brands have a very good battery system as it doesn't drain fast. Uganda as country faces load shedding and some parts of the country don't even have electricity to charge the phones. The companies however have options like charging the phones using solar energy and this highly benefits the people who are living in parts of the country where electricity doesn't reach. This acts as a big competitive advantage benefit to these phone brands. Samsung and Apple phones cannot charge using solar energy as it's too weak for their operating systems. Transsion's increasing level of brand orientation in the awareness competencies brander shows a level of progression in brand communication. The achievement competencies branders have a high level of brand orientation, they are larger in size and more active in and committed to branding. The progression in brand competence partially relates to a firm's business nature and size. Brand competence firms like Transsion are usually those who have developed a determinable business scale, and their business nature requires them to develop a distinctive brand to compete in the market. These phones have penetrated the market as the evidence I see in the hands of most Ugandans carrying mobile phones be low end phones or smart phones, chances are high that more than five are holding a Techno model. Techno's immense popularity with price sensitive Ugandans is that no self-respecting Ugandan fails to secure himself a trusty Techno phone, with its dual Sim, radio, flashlights, clear picture etc....features, that are Chinese managed cram onto these but nice-looking devices.

China's partnership with African start-ups is a form of social responsibility. Its deal on making African infrastructure and commodities further boosted in recent years as Beijing pushes its Belt and Road plan. Transsion's IPO was the second event last year after Chinese owned OPERA venture spending in Africa (Nigeria). This furthermore reflects greater Chinese influence and investment in the continent's digital scene.

Africa the next China

Transsions rise in Africa comes after as the Chinese conglomerates are making the most of the continent's need for technology, trade, manufacturing and infrastructure. The increased interest in

Africa also arises amid growing Sino African political economic relations with growing diplomatic links, investments in much needed infrastructure like roads and airports, increasing tourism, the provision of scholarship and training, the promotion of win win economic cooperation policy besides mutual assistance in security matters For African governments, investments from companies like Transsion have meant believing in mobile telephony crucial role to kickstart and motivate grassroots innovations. In the world's youngest continent, there's the binding belief now that digital technologies can spur economic growth and disrupt some of the industries. China, which has emerged as an innovation powerhouse thanks to companies like Tencent, Baidu, and Alibaba has made strategic moves to invest in nations like Ethiopia and Zimbabwe. Bent on becoming the world leader in artificial intelligence, Chinese firms like Guangzhou based start up cloud walk want to improve their facial recognition software by collecting data from Africans. Transsion's success has also helped draw in some of China's star domestic phone brands to Africa. The multinational telecoms company ZTE unveiled TempoGO, an 80\$ smartphone with Android software aimed at Africa as the primary market. From 2015, the electronics multinational Xiaomi started selling its phones through distributors in African nations including Uganda, Nigeria and South Africa. The Chinese conglomerate TCL also sells cheap phone models and smart watches in the continent Transsion's strong growth potential is vivid in the market and its future will probably continue to be wrapped up with that of African development.

Conclusion

Brand positioning is built on a foundation of great strategies. Transsion mobiles is on a winning streak, not just in East Africa but globally. Last year when they stepped into the international scene for the first time, several people questioned their tactics and critiqued our model but one year after, it has become even more evident that Transsion's ability to develop globally competitive products with deep local consumer insight is an essential ingredient in our dominance globally.

It plays a crucial role while deciding the strategy of an organization. Chinese companies took initiatives to understand what consumers want, understand what their brand capabilities are and finally understood how each competitor is positioning their brand then they reflect this brand positioning in everything that they did. As a result, Chinese mobile brands has become leading, convenient and affordable mobile phones brand. In the coming years, China will be highly known for selling smartphones and providing VC for African start-ups.

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